

SANOAT KORXONALARI RAHBAR VA MUTAXASSISLARINING MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI BO'YICHA BILIMLARINI TEKSHIRISHNI RAQAMLI TEXNALOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Sanoat korxonalarini rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo'yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish va bu orqali erishiladigan natijalar haqida muallifning ilmiy izlanishlari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar va iboralar: Raqamlashtirish, o'quv dasturi, interaktiv uslub, raqamli texnologiya, onlayn o'qitish, ma'lumotlar ombori.

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ORGANIZING THE EXAMINATION OF KNOWLEDGE OF LABOR PROTECTION OF MANAGERS AND SPECIALISTS OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES ON THE BASIS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Abstract. The scientific research of the author about the organization of the examination of the knowledge of the leaders and specialists of industrial enterprises on labor protection on the basis of digital technologies and the results achieved through this is described.

Key words and phrases: Digitization, curriculum, interactive style, digital technology, online learning, data warehouse.

ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ПРОВЕРКИ ЗНАНИЙ ОХРАНЫ ТРУДА РУКОВОДИТЕЛЕЙ И СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация. Описаны научные исследования автора по организации проверки знаний руководителей и специалистов промышленных предприятий по охране труда на основе цифровых технологий и достигнутые за счет этого результаты.

Ключевые слова и фразы: Цифровизация, учебная программа, интерактивный стиль, цифровые технологии, онлайн-обучение, хранилище данных.

KIRISH. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bandlik va mehnat munosabatlari vazirligi (2017 yilgacha O'zbekiston Respublikasi Mehnat va ijtimoiy himoya vazirligi deya nomlangan) tomonidan tasdiqlanib O'zbekiston Respublikasi Adliya Vazirligi tomonidan 1996 yil 14 avgustda 272- raqam bilan ruyxatga olingan “Mehnat muhofazasi bo'yicha o'qitish va bilimlarni tekshirish to'g'risida namunaviy nizom”ga [1] muvofiq rahbarlar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo'yicha bilimlari darajasini oshirish maqsadida boshqaruv organlari va korxonalarda davlat kuzatuv organlari, mehnat muhofazasi ilmiy-tadqiqot institutlari va tarmoq ilmiy-tadqiqot institutlari mutaxassislarini jalb qilgan holda kurslar, seminarlar, ma'ruzalar, konsultatsiyalar tashkil qilinishi belgilab berilgan.

Sanoat korxonalari rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo'yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish samarali hisoblanadi[2]. Bunda har bir rahbar va xodimlarning lavozim va mutaxassislik, ish faoliyati turidan kelib chiqib mehnatni muhofaza qilishga o'qitish kurslarini masofaviy shaklda tashkil etish orqali xodimlarning ish vaqtidan ajralmasdan interaktiv uslubda yaratish orqali amalga oshirishni tashkil etish munkun.

Mehnatni muhofaza qilish sohasidagi raqamlashtirish odatda aqlli kaskalar, sun'iy intellekt orqali xavflarni aniqlash vositalari va VR ta'lim texnologiyalarini anglatadi, shuningdek mehnatni muhofaza qilish sohasida elektron hujjat aylanishi va elektron raqamli imzodan foydalanish yordamida hujjatlar bilan ishlashni soddalashtirish, ish joyida mehnatni muhofaza qilish madaniyati darajasini oshirish, xodimlarning huquqlarini himoya qilish va yuqori xavflilikdagi ishlar xavfsizligini ta'minlashda xam muhim rol o'ynaydi[3].

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI: Mamlakatimizda sanoat korxonalarida mehnat muhofazasini tashkil etish hamda mehnat muhofazasi va xavfsizlik texnikasi bo'yicha o'qitish va xodimlar bilimini sinovdan o'tkazish masalalari Yuldoshev O'.R, Yormatov G.Yo. Isamuxamedov Yo.U., Zokirova N.Q., Abduraxmonov Q. X. Irmatova A. B. Yunusov B.X. kabi olimlarning o'quv va ilmiy adabiyotlarida o'z aksini topgan.

MDH davlatlari korxonalarda mehnat muhofazasini raqamlashtirish masalalari bo'yicha Kovrigo O.V., Timofeev A.V., Ryabova V. Ye., Faynburg G. Z., Ivanov S. Yu., Kalagin I., Titov A., IJemelinin V., Porochkin D., Kuchumova G. V., Melyakova O. A., 13. Shabunin K. sarev V., Vesnin Ye., Soloveva A., Venediktova A. ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarini olib borishgan.

Raqamli iqtisodiyotning nazariy asoslari xorijlik olim va mutaxassislardan M.A.Shneps-Shneppe, D.Ye. Namiot, P.Vinya, M.Keyn, N.Popper, Ye.Filippov, A. Fork, L.V. Lapidus, D.Bell, M.Kastels, V.Desouza, D.Makkonaz, M.Linch, S.Dirikan, S.Xalford, M.Savaj kabi xorijlik iqtisodchi olimlarning ilmiy tadqiqotlarida atroflicha yoritilgan. Jumladan, iqtisodchi olimlar M.A.Shneps-Shneppe va Namiot D.Ye. o'zining tadqiqotlarida qator Raqamli iqtisodiyot, telekommunikatsiya - rivojlanishning asosiy bo'g'ini ekanligi va uning xususiyatlari to'g'risida nazariyalarini tadqiq etib o'tishgan. L.V. Lapidus o'z tadqiqotlarida raqamli texnologiyalar evolyusiyasi ta'siri ostida biznes modellarini o'zgartirish nuqtai nazaridan elektron biznes va elektron tijoratni boshqarish bo'yicha nazariy qoidalar va amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

O'zbekistonlik olimlardan S.S.G'ulomov, R.H.Ayupov, G.R.Boltaboeva, T.Shodiev, T.Z. Teshabaev, Z.M. Otakuzieva, Sh.Mustafaqulov, R.S.Urunov, M.Yu.Jumaniyozova, Z.M.Qurbonov, U.M.Asraevlar ishlarida raqamli iqtisodiyotning nazariy asoslari bayon etilgan. Xususan, Sh.Mustafaqulov o'zining ilmiy izlanishlarida rivojlanishning yangi tendensiyalari va xususiyatlari atroflicha yoritilgan.

TADQIQOT METODLARI. Tadqiqot jarayonida ilmiy va o'quv-uslubiy adabiyotlar tahlili, pedagogik kuzatuv, qiyosiy tahlil, umumlashtirish, dasturlashtirish va raqaamlashtirish modellari kabi metodlardan foydalanildi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI VA MUHOKAMALAR. Mehnatni muhofaza qilish tizimlari haqida ko'plab ma'lumotlar mavjud, shuningdek, ularni raqamlashtirish tizimi ham mavjud. Bu tizimlar faoliyatining xususiyatlari va turiga qarab o'zgartirib boriladi, shuningdek, o'z faoliyati bo'yicha xususiyatlari bo'yicha ham farqlanadi.

Mehnatni muhofaza qilish tizimlari raqamlashtirish asosida barcha ishlab chiqarish va xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining mehnat faoliyati sifatini oshirish uchun amalga oshiriladi. Bu tizimlarning yagona maqsadi - ishchi va mehnat faoliyati bo'lgan turdagi turli tarkibdagi organlarda mehnat muhofazasini takomillashtirish va ishchilarni kasbiy mehnat muhofazasi yo'riqnomlaridan o'tkazishdir. Bu maqsadga erishish uchun, tizimlarda faoliyatni boshqarish va uning joriy holatini ta'kidlash imkonini beradigan statistik ma'lumotlar jamlanadi.

Bu raqamlashtirish tizimlari to'plangan va ishlovchi shaxslar haqidagi tafsilotli ma'lumotlarni saqlaydi, shu jumladan, ularning tashkiliy qurilmalari, kasbiy tayyorliklari va amaliyotlari, ta'lim va tajriba darajalari, ishga kirish va ishdan chiqish sanalari, ta'til, dam olish vaqtlari haqida ma'lumotlar va bularni qaysi asosda tashkil etilganligi haqidagi ma'lumotlardir[4].

Tizim, mehnat muhofazasini ta'minlash va muhofaza qilishga odatlangan yondashuvlar, yangi ishchilarning ishga qabul qilinishi, mehnatda ishlayotgan ishchilar soni, ularning bilim va tajribasi kabi ko'plab yunalishlarda yordam beradi.

Mehnatni muhofaza qilishni o'qitishga yo'naltirilgan raqamlashtirish tizimlari, ishchi va mehnat faoliyati bo'yicha kasbiy tayyorlanishni oshirishga va xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Bu tizimlar, mehnat faoliyatining xususiyatlarini va turini hisobga olgan holda faoliyatni o'zgartirish va yangilashga yordam berish maqsadida yaratiladi.

Mehnatda xavfsizlikni ta'minlashga ko'rsatilgan e'tibor raqamlashtirish tizimlarida katta ahamiyatga ega. Bu tizimlar ishchi va mehnat faoliyati bo'yicha xavfsizlik masalalariga e'tibor qaratishni o'rganuvchilar va o'qituvchilar uchun yordam beradi.

XULOSA. Sanoat korxonalari rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo'yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish, bir nechta maqsadlarga erishishga yordam berishi mumkin:

1. Ish faoliyatining nazoratini yaxshilash: Raqamli texnologiyalar foydalanilganda, korxonalar rahbarlari va mutaxassislarining ishchi muhofazasi bo'yicha bilimlari va ko'nikmalari yordamida, korxonaning ish rejimida yuzaga keladigan muammo va muammo bo'lmagan holatlarni nazorat qilish osonlashadi.

2. Qo'shimcha resurslarni ishlatish: Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali, mehnat muhofazasi sohasida katta miqdorda ma'lumotlar to'planishi mumkin. Bu ma'lumotlar orqali korxonalar rahbarlari va mutaxassislarining ish rejimini yanada yaxshilash, barcha resurslarni yaxshilash, o'zaro hamkorlikni oshirish va mahsulot sifatini ko'paytirish mumkin.

3. Tahmin qilish: Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali korxonaning ish rejimida yuzaga keladigan muammo va muammo bo'lmagan holatlarning tasvirlash, shunchaki, sifatli ma'lumotlar yig'ish yordamida korxonalar rahbarlari va mutaxassislarining xavfsizlik, avvalgi sharoitlarni o'rganish va o'zgarishlarga ta'sir ko'rsatish qobiliyatini oshirish mumkin.

4. Ko'nikma va texnikani yaxshilash: Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali korxonadagi mutaxassislar va hodimlar yaratish, tarbiyalash va ko'nikma olish uchun muhtojliklarini aniqlash mumkin. Bu shuningdek, qo'shimcha texnikaviy imkoniyatlardan ham foydalanish mumkin.

5. Muammolar yechish: Raqamli texnologiyalar orqali, korxonaning muammolarini aniqlash, yechish va uning faoliyatini yanada yaxshilash uchun yordam berish mumkin. Bu esa, korxonalar rahbarlari va mutaxassislarining barcha sohalarini rivojlantirishga imkon beradi.

6. O‘qitishni osonlashtirish: Mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish orqali xodimlarni ishdan ajralmagan holda o‘z bilimlarini oshirish, qayta tayyorlovdan o‘tishlarini taminlash mumkin.

7. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishga yunaltirilgan mablag‘larni tejab qolish: Mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish orqali, xodimlarni o‘qitish va bilimini sinashga sarflanadigan mag‘lag‘larni tejab qolish mumkin.

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